

The RiverCure Portal and Citizen Science: Usability Assessment Guide

In the context of my Master's Dissertation, I extended the features of the RiverCure Portal to accommodate use and contribution from citizens. In order to assess the usability of the Portal, I ask that you complete a set of tasks, as well as respond to the questionnaire available here, after completing the tasks.

The completion of the guide should take about 10 minutes, and the questionnaire should take about 5 minutes.

The provision of personal data is voluntary and will be kept in accordance with the GDPR. No data will be shared with third parties.

Thank you for your participation!

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* Indicates required question

What is your age? *

- < 15
- 15 - 19
- 20 - 24
- 25 - 29
- 30 - 34
- 35 - 39
- > 39

What is your gender? *

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- I prefer not to say
- Other:

What level of education are you attending? *

- 1st Cycle (Bachelor's)
- 2nd Cycle (Master's)
- 3rd Cycle (Doctoral)

What is your area of study? *

Your answer

I think that I would like to use the portal frequently. *

- | | | | | | | |
|-------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|----------------|
| | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | |
| Strongly Disagree | <input type="radio"/> | Strongly Agree |

I found the portal unnecessarily complex. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

I thought the portal was easy to use. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use the portal. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

I found the various functions in the portal were well integrated. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

I thought there was too much inconsistency in the portal. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

I would imagine that most people would learn to use the portal very quickly. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

I found the portal very awkward to use. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

I felt very confident using the portal. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with the portal. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

I preferred using the map, instead of the grid, to find the "Coura-Questionário-Usabilidade" Context. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

Additional comments/opinions?

Your answer

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